

Master in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Research and Evaluation of Automatic Sound FX Classification in Freesound using the Universal Category System

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Supervisor: Frederic Font

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Abstract

Automatic sound classification is becoming increasingly important across domains in audio and music, particularly in the use of sound FX libraries for video and audio post-production. The Universal Category System (UCS) has recently been adopted as the industry standard for organizing and classifying sound FX, yet the performance of UCS-based classifiers in real-world scenarios remains underexplored. This thesis builds upon prior work on UCS-based sound classification and investigates how different methodologies can enhance classifier performance, with a focus on real-world user-generated data from Freesound. As part of this work, a custom Freesound dataset was built to enable evaluation under realistic conditions, alongside a professionally curated dataset. The study compares a range of models and demonstrates that while strong results are achieved on curated data, performance drops considerably on heterogeneous real-world audio, highlighting domain transfer challenges such as inconsistent metadata, variable quality, and semantic ambiguity. Fine-tuning on the custom dataset led to some improvements, particularly for multimodal models, but performance remained far from ideal, showing that adaptation alone is not sufficient to overcome domain gaps. Overall, this work contributes both a new dataset and an in-depth evaluation of UCS-based classification, while also pointing to future directions in embedding design, multimodal integration, and domain-aware training for more robust and transferable sound classification systems in practical applications.

Keywords: Sound Classification, Universal Category System, Domain Transfer, Multi-modal learning

Chapter 1

Introduction

Sounds are one of the most important aspects in human life, the way we perceive and identify sounds everyday is a deeply complex and intuitive process. From footsteps in a hallway to a ringtone or vibration of a phone on a desk, people are able to perceive, identify and make sense of sounds not only based on their acoustic characteristics but also based on the surrounding environments, past experiences and situational expectations. This internal process of identifying and recognizing - sometimes conscious and sometimes subconsciously is inherently a form of **Sound Classification**. For instance, a dog's bark is not only recognized by its sound waveform, it is understood based on how and where it's heard from - whether it's in a park or through a window in a house, or through a speaker as well.

In recent years, with the drastic growth of digital media, the need to being able to replicate this ability of nuanced sound classifications has grown significantly. Audio and sound are essentially one of the most important aspects in multimedia content like video games, movies, songs, audio-books, virtual reality, social media and so on. **Sound effects (SFX)** has become a crucial part in the creation of digital media and plays a major role in creating more immersive environments. This rapid growth of digital content creation has gradually resulted in the creation of extensive sound libraries across various domains. Some notable libraries include **Pro Sound Effects (PSE)**, **Freesound**[1], BBC Sound Effects, Boom library and more. These

libraries are built and curated using various different sources including professional recordings, field capturing, and even user submissions in platforms like Freesound. However, while these large sound libraries provide invaluable resources, effective management and classification of such diverse and rapidly growing libraries remain a challenge. Although standardized taxonomies like the Universal Category System (UCS)[2] have proven effective in professional datasets like PSE, their performance on more diverse, community-driven platforms where sound quality, metadata, and labeling practices vary significantly remains limited. This gap highlights the need for further research and investigation.

1.1 Motivation

As the digital age progresses, media content grows at an unprecedented rate, and similarly the number of available sound samples has expanded drastically. This growth not only includes sound samples in professionally produced and curated audio content like PSE, but also user generated sounds recorded and shared through online platforms like Freesound[1] where there are currently more than 670,000 plus audio recordings that vary in quality, recording conditions, equipments used, how and where it was recorded. Efficiently being able to organize, retrieve, and utilize these sounds in creative workflows requires Automatic Sound Classification systems that are both scalable and versatile. Such systems must be capable of handling the high variability of real-world data, including differences in noise levels, recording devices like mics, and metadata. Additionally, they should be able to support efficient and fast search and retrieval to meet the expectations and workflows of professional sound designers and content creators who would rely on quick access to relevant sounds with these rapidly growing libraries.

In order to have efficient and consistent organization of sound libraries, various heterogeneous taxonomies have been developed [3]. One example is the **Broad Sound Taxonomy (BST)**[4] which was recently introduced to Freesound as its organizational scheme, featuring a high-level semantic structure. The **AudioSet Ontology** [5] provides more fine-grained categorization with a deeper hierarchical

structure, containing event classes organized in a tree-like taxonomy. The **Universal Category System (UCS)** [2] was developed to be comprehensive from a sound effects (SFX) perspective, specifically tailored for professional sound effects libraries and post-production workflows. UCS provides a comprehensive hierarchical framework for labeling and categorizing sound effects, using consistent naming conventions across large libraries. This standardized taxonomy makes classification more efficient by improving search, retrieval, and management, crucial in professional environments where consistency is key. In curated libraries such as the **PSE Library** \cite{prosoundeffects_upf} and the **BBC Sound Effects Archive** \cite{bbc_sound_effects}, models trained with UCS labels achieve high accuracy thanks to the availability of high-quality recordings, consistent formats, well-structured metadata, and relatively balanced class distributions—all factors that support strong classifier performance.

However, significant challenges are faced when attempting to apply similar classification algorithms to user-generated content platforms such as Freesound where sounds are uploaded by various users who may use a variety of recording equipments ranging from mobile phones to high-end professional recording microphones. Consequently, the audio content on these platforms are also recorded in very different environments, spanning a range from studio-quality recordings to noisy, low-quality samples in drastically varying acoustic environments.

Moreover, these sounds are uploaded along with descriptions and metadata tags that could vary significantly depending on how one person would perceive or understand those particular sounds. Some users could provide very detailed and accurate annotations, while most other sounds could suffer from inconsistent or even misleading metadata, which eventually leads to complicating the use of classification methods that rely on audio and text information. This variability introduces a major challenge in automatic sound classification models, challenging their ability to generalize and maintain accuracy across such diverse data.

Together, these factors introduce several practical and technical challenges for automatic sound classification:

- **Domain gap:** The most critical issue is the significant domain mismatch between training data and real-world samples. A model trained on professionally recorded, clean audio is likely to misclassify or fail entirely when exposed to low-quality, noisy, or acoustically varying recordings from everyday settings.
- **Metadata Variability:** Textual information of the sounds such as titles, tags, and descriptions of the sound can enhance classification through multi-modal models[6]. However, in community-driven platforms, this metadata is usually inconsistent or sometimes even incorrect. This metadata variability weakens the model's ability to leverage text alongside audio.
- **Label Subjectivity:** Human perception of sounds is very context dependent and subjective. "What one person recognizes as 'clapping,' another might label as 'applause' or 'hand percussion' or what one person tags as "storm", another might tag as "rain". This ambiguity in labeling creates label noise in training data and leads to confusion in model predictions. At the same time, It also raises a philosophical question about the "correctness" of a tag in the absence of a ground truth.
- **Class Imbalance:** In many user-generated datasets, certain sound categories dominate while others are rarer. For example, everyday sounds like footsteps, city noise, nature sounds or phone notifications may appear frequently, while niche or more context-specific sounds are usually lesser in number. This may lead to unbalanced learning, where classification systems may favor overrepresented classes and neglect smaller ones.
- **Scalability:** Beyond research accuracy, there's also the motivation of building tools that are functionally reliable in professional environments. Sound designers, music producers, and developers increasingly rely on accurately searchable sound libraries, tagging systems, and audio retrieval tools. For these systems to be genuinely useful in real-world applications, they must function effectively across even with unstructured and unpredictable datasets.

These converge on a key research question - can sound classification systems de-

signed around professional datasets and taxonomies like UCS be adapted to work effectively on noisy and highly variable user-generated sound libraries? By investigating this problem, this thesis aims to contribute towards better understanding of sound classification and also to a broader goal of making intelligent automatic sound classification systems that are deployable across diverse environments.

1.2 Key Concepts

1.2.1 Automatic Sound Classification (ASC)

Automatic Sound Classification refers to the use of computational algorithms to manage, classify, and retrieve sound effects by automatically assigning meaningful labels to audio recordings, mimicking the human ability to recognize and categorize sounds. Unlike humans, who classify sounds intuitively through context and experience, machines depend on large, annotated datasets created by human experts. These labeled recordings form the foundation for training models using signal processing, machine learning, or deep learning techniques. Through this process, systems learn to detect patterns in audio and perform accurate classifications. Typically, the workflow begins with pre-processing, where raw recordings are cleaned, standardized, and segmented. Next, features are extracted from the waveform in a structured format suitable for computation. Finally, machine learning or deep learning algorithms associate these features with sound labels. Automatic sound classification has broad applications, including environmental monitoring, medical diagnosis (e.g., respiratory sound analysis), music information retrieval, security systems, and biodiversity research through automated species identification.

1.2.2 Semantics and Acoustic Features

In sound classification, both acoustic features of a sound and its semantic information such as title, tags and description play a vital role in understanding and categorizing audio content. Acoustic features refer to measurable information extracted from an audio waveform, such as spectral shape, spectral energy, pitch, dynamics or

temporal features. These features are often represented using Mel-frequency cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs), log-Mel spectrograms, or learned embeddings that capture the various properties of a sound and are essential for models that use audio as a basis.

On the other hand, semantic features derive from human-annotated metadata like titles, tags and descriptions, often offering context and meaning beyond a raw audio signal. For example, for a sound that has rain noise, a tag like "rain", "water", "rainfall" helps provide meaningful context and disambiguate between acoustically similar sounds.

Acoustic features typically exist in high-dimensional spaces and capture temporal-spectral patterns, while semantic features operate in conceptual spaces where relationships between categories can be learned through word embeddings or ontological structures. At the same time acoustic features are sensitive to recording conditions, background noise, and signal quality, whereas semantic features remain consistent across different audio recordings of the same conceptual category. This makes semantic features valuable for generalization across diverse recording environments and other variable factors.

1.2.3 Multimodal learning

Multimodal learning refers to the process of modeling information from multiple data sources or modalities, in this scenario of sound classification, this would involve acoustic and semantic features of a sound.

In multi-modal systems, combining these two modalities, acoustic and semantic features, can enhance classification performance, especially in noisy or ambiguous scenarios where one modality alone may be insufficient. By combining these modalities, the system would aim to use complementary strengths where audio features could provide detailed signal-level information and text/semantic features could provide high level information about the audio [6].

Multimodal systems show better robustness compared to unimodal approaches as

they can maintain performance even when one modality is degraded. For instance if audio quality is poor due to background noise, semantic features from metadata can compensate, and vice versa when textual descriptions are incorrect or ambiguous.

1.2.4 Freesound

Freesound is an open, collaborative database platform where users can upload and share audio recordings ranging from everyday sounds to experimental synthesized textures with over 670,000 plus user-contributed audio samples. It serves as a vast library of audio resource for sound designers, researchers and artists. The platform uses advanced technologies for classification of sound, retrieval and search, leveraging the Essentia audio analysis library to automatically extract acoustic features from uploaded sounds and the similarity search engine for content-based retrieval. Additionally, Freesound has recently implemented the Broad Sound Taxonomy (BST)[7] as its organizational scheme. This enables users to find sounds through traditional text-based searches, as well as Query-by-Example functionality, where users can upload audio files to find acoustically similar sounds based on spectral, timbral and other acoustic characteristics.

1.2.5 Universal Category System (UCS)

The Universal Category System (UCS) is a standardized hierarchical taxonomy developed to organize and label SFX in professional audio environments. It consists of around 82 top-level categories with over 700 sub-categories, allowing for consistent naming and structure across various levels which enables a uniform structure in commercial sound libraries.

1.2.6 Evaluation metrics and Performance Assessment

Performance evaluation in automatic sound classification relies on several key metrics that provide different perspectives on system performance. These metrics are important for assessing the classification performance and accuracy and assess if there are any imbalances.

Accuracy

Accuracy represents the proportion of correctly classified samples over the total number of samples:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Predictions}}$$

where TP (True Positives), TN (True Negatives), FP (False Positives), and FN (False Negatives) represent the counts from the confusion matrix.

Balanced Accuracy

Balanced accuracy addresses the limitations of standard accuracy by computing the average recall obtained on each class, providing equal weight to each class (balanced) regardless of its frequency:

$$\text{Balanced Accuracy} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{TP}{TP + FN} + \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \right)$$

For multi-class problems with C classes, this extends to:

$$\text{Balanced Accuracy} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{i=1}^C \frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FN_i}$$

This metric is particularly valuable for sound classification tasks where certain categories may be underrepresented in the dataset.

F1-Score

The F1-score provides the harmonic mean of precision and recall, offering a single metric that balances both measures:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

$$\text{F1-Score} = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} = \frac{2 \cdot TP}{2 \cdot TP + FP + FN}$$

The F1-score is particularly useful when both false positives and false negatives carry significant costs, making it well-suited for sound classification applications where both precision and recall are important.

Weighted F1-Score

For multi-class classification problems, the weighted F1-score computes the F1-score for each class and then calculates a weighted average based on the support (number of true instances) for each class:

$$\text{F1-Score}_{\text{weighted}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^C n_i \cdot \text{F1-Score}_i$$

where N is the total number of samples, C is the number of classes, n_i is the number of samples in class i , and F1-Score_i is the F1-score for class i . This metric accounts for class imbalance by giving more weight to classes with more samples which is important in datasets with class imbalances.

Confusion Matrix

The confusion matrix provides a comprehensive view of classification performance by showing the actual versus predicted classifications for each class. For a multi-class problem with C classes, the confusion matrix M is a $C \times C$ matrix where:

$$M_{i,j} = \text{number of samples with true label } i \text{ predicted as label } j$$

The confusion matrix enables detailed analysis of classification errors, revealing

which classes are most commonly confused with each other. For sound classification, this is useful for identifying acoustically or semantically similar categories that the system struggles to differentiate.

1.3 Objectives

The main objective of this thesis is to investigate the practical applicability of standardized taxonomies, specifically the Universal Category System (UCS), for ASC in real-world, user generated audio environments. While prior research has demonstrated high classification accuracy in controlled and professionally curated datasets, there is limited understanding of how these systems would perform in community-driven platforms such as Freesound. This thesis aims to bridge that gap through the following specific objectives:

- **Enhance and refine already existing classifiers:** To improve and refine already existing classifiers like MLP for sound classification systems using additional embeddings and data accordingly for better performance.
- **Assess domain transfer effectiveness:** Evaluate how well UCS-based classifiers trained on professionally curated datasets such as Pro Sound Effects (PSE150K), generalize to user-generated content from Freesound. Analyze the performance degradation caused by domain shift and analyze its implications for classification.
- **Evaluate the role of multimodal learning:** Implement and evaluate unimodal and multi-modal classification architectures to assess how different modalities contribute to predictive performance. Determine the relative contribution of audio and textual metadata in classification tasks and evaluate their effectiveness.
- **Provide valuable insights for practical deployment:** Research and investigate possible directions towards designing more robust and generalizable ASC systems that can work with varied datasets and audio content.

- **Develop a dataset for cross-domain evaluation:** Construct and make publicly available a custom built UCS-organized Freesound dataset that allows for evaluation of domain transfer from professional to user-generated audio content. This dataset contribution aims to enable future research, to conduct standardized comparisons and understanding of domain adaptation challenges in sound classification systems.

The custom Freesound dataset and code publicly available¹ for further research.

1.4 Structure of the Report

The remainder of this thesis is organized as follows:

Chapter 2: State of the Art - This chapter discusses the history of automatic sound classification systems, from traditional signal processing approaches to deep learning techniques, including current approaches that are used. It also introduces key technologies, taxonomies and models relevant to this study.

Chapter 3: Methodology - This chapter outlines the breakdown of the experiments and procedures used throughout this research. Provides explanations of the dataset collection, pre-processing steps, model configurations and evaluation methodologies.

Chapter 4: Results - This chapter presents the outcomes of the experiments, including performance metrics and observations. The key findings are highlighted and compared across different models and data conditions.

Chapter 5: Discussion - This chapter describes and analyzes the results obtained from all the experiments, while trying to interpret and understand the implications of the results in the context of real-world sound classification.

Chapter 6: Conclusion - This final chapter summarizes the main contributions and findings of the thesis. Discussing on the broader significance of the work, along with suggestions for possible future improvements in sound classification systems.

¹https://github.com/MadhavJ06/freesound_ucs.git

Chapter 2

State of the Art

The field of automatic sound classification has evolved significantly over the past two decades, driven by advances in signal processing, machine learning, and the growing availability of large-scale audio datasets. This chapter provides a comprehensive review of the current state-of-the-art in automatic sound classification, with particular emphasis on sound effects classification, taxonomic systems, and multimodal approaches that combine acoustic and semantic features.

Finally, we identify possible gaps in the current literature, particularly the lack of systematic evaluation frameworks for cross-domain sound effect classification and the limited exploration of UCS-based taxonomic classification in user-generated content scenarios. This analysis establishes the foundation for the methodological contributions presented in the following chapters and puts this research within the broader context of automatic sound classification and audio content organization.

2.1 History of Sound Classification

Early research in sound classification drew from various branches of study such as cognitive sciences and psychoacoustics, where the goal was to understand how humans perceived and distinguished sounds. These early studies focused on identifying perceptual features such as pitch, timbre and temporal structures which enabled

humans to differentiate sounds. This work laid the foundation for computational models by establishing key acoustic properties that influence auditory perception and classification.

Initial works began with a focus on pitch perception for sound classification researches. Helmholtz's place theory and Terhardt's harmonic template model[8][9] demonstrated how our brain and auditory system are stimulated differently according to the frequencies and tonal qualities in a sound. Risset and Chowning developed computational models[10][11] that analyzed sounds based on their spectral envelopes. These spectral profiles were used to distinguish between different instruments.

Theories of categorization in cognitive psychology have significantly influenced sound classification research. Gestalt's principles by Wertheimer[12] explain how humans organize auditory stimuli into meaningful patterns, such as grouping environmental sounds into a single category. Rosch's prototype theory[13] suggests categorization is based on resemblance to a familiar or proper association to a sound, similar to how musical genres are identified and categorized by humans. Bergman introduced Auditory Scene Analysis[14] which describes how humans perceive complex soundscapes by being able to segregate and analyze different auditory elements. These studies provided the conceptual framework and foundations for the development of computational methods to analyze sounds based on their spectral characteristics.

2.2 Current Approaches

2.2.1 Machine learning based approaches

In early stages while adopting machine learning (ML) methodologies for sound classification, handcrafted features such as Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) [15] were widely used for feature extraction. These features formed the basis for traditional machine learning models, including Hidden Markov Models (HMMs), Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs)

Covreur et al.[16] developed an environmental noise recognition system based on time-frequency analysis using HMMs, showcasing that these systems were able to outperform the average human listener in distinguishing noise types. In a different study, Baumann et al.[17] classified audio into four broad categories – clean speech, speech in noise, noise and music using spectral and harmonicity-based features using a HMM model. HMMs were widely used in early classification tasks due to their ability to model temporal dependencies in audio sequences. Casey M.[18] developed a HMM-based sound classification framework using the temporal evolution of audio spectra for environmental sound recognition, music instrument classification, which was incorporated into the MPEG-7 standard for multimedia content description.

Another ML methodology that was found to be popular was SVMs, due to their ability to handle high dimensional feature spaces, making them suitable for classifying complex audio data. Lu et al.[19] applied SVMs to segment and classify continuous audio streams into silence, music, background noise, pure speech, and non-pure speech. Chien-Chang et al.[20] extended this approach by incorporating wavelet-derived features, pitch information, and frequency cepstral coefficients, demonstrating their effectiveness on the MuscleFish dataset. Jia-Ching Wang et al.[21] explored this further by introducing a hybrid SVM/K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) classifier for environmental sound classification leveraging the strengths of both models, outperforming traditional HMM-based classifiers.

GMMs provided a probabilistic framework for modeling the distributions of audio features in a sound. Bahoura et al.[22] used cepstral analysis with GMMs to distinguish respiratory sounds, successfully categorizing them into breathing and wheezing. Roch et al[23] used GMMs to classify animal sounds, particularly dolphin vocalizations, highlighting the applicability in bioacoustics research.

With proven strengths in using hybrid systems, Rajapakse et al.[24] demonstrated that a GMM-HMM hybrid models outperformed traditional standalone methodologies by integrating GMM-based probabilistic feature modeling with HMM-driven temporal structure learning. Vacher et al.[25] explored a GMM-HMM hybrid system in a smart room context for sound classification and speech recognition to assist

patient monitoring in hospitals.

2.2.2 Deep learning based approaches

More recently with the breakthrough in deep learning (DL) based methodologies, classification systems have significantly improved and scaled up in terms of efficiency due to DL approaches. These models discover latent patterns in spectral and temporal structures that often surpass human-designed features in classification problems.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) emerged as a particularly effective and popular architecture which demonstrated success in learning representational features in audio. CNNs process data as images, hence in the case of audio, it is first converted into a spectrogram, which serves as a visual representation of the audio's frequency content over time. This processing reduces dimensionality of the data while enabling the model to generalize and learn the features, making it more efficient in handling a wide range of sounds. Studies by Hershey et al.[26], Salamon et al.[27] and Piczak[28] showcased the effectiveness of CNNs in sound classification for different scenarios, particularly when trained on large audio datasets.

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), particularly Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTMs) have proven to be effective for modeling temporal dependencies in sound. These architectures excel at capturing sequential patterns in a long-term context, which is crucial for tasks where the order, structure and timing of sounds matter. Bae et al.[29], Bubashait et al.[30] and Bahmei et al.[31] demonstrated how RNNs and LSTMs when combined with CNNs, benefit from using the strengths of both the architectures in handling both spatial and temporal aspects of audio. These systems were particularly useful in healthcare monitoring systems such as heart, respiratory sound classifications[32].

More recently transformer-based models were illustrated for feature extraction. Chen et al.[33] used attention-based transformer models, which focus on selectively processing relevant portions of the input audio. These models rely on attention mechanisms, allowing the network to capture the relevant features and patterns of the

input, improving its ability to distinguish between different sound classes.

Transfer learning has also emerged as a powerful methodology in deep learning-based audio classification systems, particularly when labeled data is scarce. By using pre-trained models such as CNNs or Transformers trained on large-scale audio datasets, classifiers can be used to adapt to new tasks with minimal fine-tuning. For instance, Hershey et al.[26] demonstrated that features extracted from CNNs pre-trained on general audio tasks generalize well to specific sound classification problems, reducing the need for domain-specific training data. This approach is valuable for our work using UCS-based classifications, where heirarchical taxonomies benefit from shared representations across various sound classes.

A recent promising advance in multimodal learning are models like **CLAP (Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining)** developed by Elizalde et al.[6] and extended by Wu et al.[34] CLAP enables zero-shot audio classification, cross-modal retrieval and versatile semantic search without task specific fine-tuning. CLAP uses both audio signal and semantic descriptions of a sound as inputs to create a vector representation that exist in a joint embedding space which allows for capturing of both acoustic and semantic representations of audio. CLAP primarily performs this using a dual-encoder framework as shown in 1 - Audio encoder which processes spectrograms (e.g. log-Mel) to extract acoustic features and the text encoder that embeds natural language descriptions (e.g. "rain"). This optimizes a shared latent space where audio-text pairs that match are pulled closer together and the mismatched pairs are pushed apart.

Figure 1: CLAP (Contrastive Language-Audio Pre-training) Architecture

The LAION-CLAP model developed by Wu et al.[34] works similar to the original CLAP model but was trained using a different dataset - LAION-Audio-630K. This used different audio and text encoders in pre-training phase and allows for dynamically combining spectral and temporal features to handle variable-length audio.

2.3 Datasets, Sound FX libraries and Taxonomy

In the early days, multiple datasets were created focusing mostly on speech and music processing. Garofolo et al. created TIMIT Acoustic-phonetic continuous Speech Corpus[35], which contains recordings of 630 speakers of different dialects of American English, which was used for speech processing. The AURORA dataset, developed by Pearce et al.[36] was used for speech recognition systems. Another popular dataset, the GTZAN music genre classification dataset, created by Tzanetakis and Cook[37] contains 100 thirty second samples in 10 different musical genres, which was widely used for music genre classification systems. Moving forward, multiple

datasets were created using the help of the Freesound library as well.

Freesound[1] is a collaborative online platform dedicated to sharing and exchange of audio samples, including sound effects, instrument samples, environmental sounds, human sounds, synthesized sounds. Freesound has a large repository of sounds with over 670,000+ audio files contributed by a community of users. Freesound employs a folksonomic tagging approach[38], enabling users to label sounds with descriptive tags. Combined with text-based search functionalities. This study by Font et al. aimed to provide more context as to the content of a sound, allowing for its more efficient usage. Freesound often engages its user community in refining its taxonomy and ontology.

Gemmek et al. developed Audioset Ontology[5] using manual annotations from an existing sound base from Youtube. Audioset ontology represents a large set of audio event classes using 632 unique classes from seven different sound families. Foncesca et al. created FSD-50K dataset[39] by manually annotating 100 hours of sounds, containing over 51,000 audio clips from Freesound. These sounds were classified and categorized into 200 classes using the AudioSet ontology[5]. More recently, Anastopoulou et al. developed the **Broad Sound Taxonomy (BST)** [4] as a simpler, more user-friendly alternative to complex hierarchical systems like AudioSet. BST consists of a two-level hierarchical structure with 5 top-level categories (*Music*, *Instrument samples*, *Speech*, *Sound effects*, and *Soundscapes*) and 23 subcategories, specifically designed to handle heterogeneous sounds with high intra-class variability. The taxonomy was developed through user studies with the Freesound community and has been officially integrated into the Freesound platform as its primary organizational scheme[7]. When users upload sounds, they must select appropriate BST categories, and previously uploaded sounds are automatically classified using machine learning algorithms trained on the Broad Sound Dataset (BSD10k)[4], which contains over 10,000 manually annotated sounds from Freesound, the technical implementation leverages semantic audio embeddings, particularly LAION-CLAP[34] representations.

The Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events (DCASE) com-

munity has highlighted the challenge of inconsistent taxonomic approaches across different audio classification tasks[40]. While some taxonomies focus on specific environmental contexts, such as the Urban Sound Taxonomy (UST) [41] which organizes urban environmental sounds into 10 classes. DCASE challenges employ even more narrowly defined task-specific taxonomies such as the ten predefined acoustic scene classes (airport, shopping mall, metro station,etc.) used in acoustic scene classification tasks. These domain-specific approaches are insufficient for general purpose sound classification. To address this need for broader coverage, taxonomies like AudioSet ontology[5] and BST[4] provides categorization across various sound classes. On the other hand **The Universal Category System (UCS)**[2] takes a more domain-specific approach while also covering a wide range of sounds, focusing exclusively on sound effects, establishing an exhaustive standardization of taxonomy for classification of SFX.

2.4 Universal Category System

UCS[2] is a public domain taxonomy for sound effects, developed by Tim Nielsen, Justin Drury and Kai Paquin in collaboration with major sound effect libraries. It aims to standardize SFX classification through hierarchical categories. Currently, in the final released version of UCS, there are 82 top level categories such as “ambience”, “impact” and 753 subcategories (e.g. “urban”, “metal”)

The top-level categories, each represent a broad noun-based classification that identifies as the primary source or context of a sound. These encompass different classes such as “fire”, “water”, “wood”, “machine” etc. These broad categories provide a fundamental organizational framework while maintaining sufficient diversity to classify a range of sounds.

The sub categories form the second layer of the taxonomical structure that serve as descriptive modifiers. These take the form of adjectives, verbs or functional nouns like “mechanical”, “movement” etc. and help to describe the top-level categories better. Unlike the unique top-level categories, these subcategories are designed to

be shared across multiple parent categories, creating a flexible vocabulary. For instance, “bells” could be part of “metal” and “music” as well or the subcategory “movement” might describe both “cloth rustling” and “plastic crumpling”, “crackle” could equally apply to the sound of burning fire or sparking electricity. This shared modifier approach efficiently mirrors how sound designers naturally describe effects in real-world practice while preventing redundancy and maintaining consistency.

Another lower level of categories present in UCS, paving to the system being more granular in nature is through Category IDs, which represent unique combinations of top-level categories and their associated subcategories. There are 457 distinct identifiers formed by algorithmically merging elements from both tiers of the hierarchy. For example, combining top-level category “Water” with subcategory “flow” will yield the category ID “WATERflow” or “WATflw”.

Category	SubCategory	CatID	CatShort	Explanations	Synonyms - Comma Separated
AIR	BLOW	AIRBlow	AIR	Steady air blows, like from a compressed can of air	Aerate, Aerosol, Air, Airhose, Balloon
AIR	BURST	AIRBst	AIR	Sharp air releases, pressure releases, a tennis ball can popping open, a fire extinguisher	Air, Airbed, Airblast, Airgun, Airhose
AIR	HISS	AIRHiss	AIR	Slow air releases, a flat tire, leak in an air pipe	Carbon, CO2, Dioxide, Discharge, Exh
AIR	MISC	AIRMisc	AIR	Air sounds not fitting another category in this list	Airtight, Airway, Carbon, CO2, Dioxide
AIR	SUCTION	AIRSuck	AIR	Air being sucked in, a vacuum sucking in air, the rush of air in a shopvac	Air, Aspirate, Aspiration, Carbon, CO
AIRCRAFT	DOOR	AERODoor	AERO	Aircraft doors, some possible overlap with other DOOR categories, or VEHICLES-DOOR	Airplane, Aviation, Boarding, Cabin,
AIRCRAFT	HELICOPTER	AEROHel	AERO	For all manner of helicopters, gyrocopters	Aerocopter, Aircraft, Apache, Auto
AIRCRAFT	INTERIOR	AEROInt	AERO	Interior recordings (mainly complex ambiances) of aircraft, from cockpit interiors, to passenger jet interiors	737, 747, 777, A310, A330, A350, A38
AIRCRAFT	JET	AEROJet	AERO	All commercial and private jet powered aircraft, military jets would go under AIRCRAFT-MILITARY	737, 747, 777, A310, A330, A350, A38
AIRCRAFT	MECHANISM	AEROMech	AERO	Mechanical components of aircraft, for example landing gear, or levers and switches.	Actuators, Aerofoil, Aeroplane, Ailer
AIRCRAFT	MILITARY	AEROMil	AERO	Military aircraft, military fighter jets, stealth bombers, but any military aircraft goes here. Also military drones. Military helicopters could go here or in AIRCRAFT-HE	A10, Aeroplane, Air, Aircraft, Airplan
AIRCRAFT	MISC	AEROMisc	AERO	Aircraft not fitting another category in this list	Aeroplane, Air, Aircraft, Airplane, Ba
AIRCRAFT	PROP	AEROProp	AERO	Aircraft using props as means of propulsion. A propeller airplane.	Aeroplane, Aircraft, Airplane, Aircre
AIRCRAFT	RADIO CONTROLLED	AERORadio	AERO	Toy hobby radio controlled, UAV, quadcopters, RC jets and RC helicopters.	Aerial, Airplane, Control, Controlled,
AIRCRAFT	ROCKET	AERORckt	AERO	Jet powered rockets and rocket engines, missiles.	Blastoff, Booster, Hypersonic, ICBM,
ALARMS	BELL	ALRMBel	ALRM	All alarms which use bells, a school bell, fire alarm bell, a railroad crossing bell.	Alarms, Alert, Bank, Burglar, Caution
ALARMS	BUZZER	ALRMBuzr	ALRM	All alarms using buzzers, or buzzers in general even if not technically an alarm, would probably go here. A front door buzzer	Alarm, Alarms, Alert, Burglar, Buzzer
ALARMS	CLOCK	ALRMClck	ALRM	Specifically alarm clocks, digital or analog. A bit of overlap with ALARMS-BELL, but clock alarms of all kinds probably best to go here	Alarm, Alarms, Analog, Clock, Digital
ALARMS	ELECTRONIC	ALRMElec	ALRM	All electronic alarms, pure electronic tone alarms. Home burglar alarms, smoke detectors, etc. Car alarms would go to VEHICLES-ALARMS	Alarms, Alert, Button, Car, Carbons, C
ALARMS	MISC	ALRMMisc	ALRM	Alarm sounds not fitting another category in this list.	Alarms, Alert, Anti-Theft, Caution, H
ALARMS	SIREN	ALRMSirn	ALRM	Mechanical sirens, like old klaxons. Vehicle sirens such as a police, fire and ambulance to go to VEHICLES-SIREN	Ahoga, Air, Air-Raid, Alarms, Blare,
AMBIENCE	AIR	AMBAir	AMB	Quiet exterior "air" with little activity, like exterior room tones, very simple exterior ambiances. The exterior equivalent of a room tone. If noticeable activity find a better	Atmos, Atmosphere, Ambience, Amn
AMBIENCE	ALPINE	AMBAlpn	AMB	Mountain ambiances, for recordings and ambiances geographically linked to Alpine Environments. Some overlap with AMBIENCE-RURAL	Alpen, Alps, Alpin, Alpine, Alpinist,
AMBIENCE	AMUSEMENT	AMBAmus	AMB	Fairground and carnivals. Beware of possible rights issues with unlicensed music. Carnivals, fairs, festivals. Probably arcades too.	Atmos, Atmosphere, Ambience, Amn
AMBIENCE	BIRDSONG	AMBBird	AMB	Group songbirds, like a dawn chorus of pretty birds, where the birds are the prominent sound. Single birds would go in BIRDS-SONGBIRD	Atmos, Atmosphere, Ambience, Amn

Figure 2: UCS Categorization example

This hierarchical structure offers several key advantages for both human users and automatic sound classification systems. As the UCS represents a widely adopted standardization effort, evaluating a classifier performance within it’s framework provides directly applicable insights for various workflows.

2.5 UCS deployment

The UCS has been widely adopted globally by professional sound libraries and audio management tools. ProSoundEffects, Soundly Pro, Krotos are libraries that offer extensive industry standard libraries (e.g. BBC sound effects, Hollywood edge) that

contain a diverse range of SFX for commercial use. These libraries are aligned with metadata according to the UCS taxonomy for precise search-ability.

As highlighted by Alison et al.[42] even UCS-compliant systems face challenges. The study addresses the challenges of inconsistent metadata and taxonomy updates in SFX libraries by proposing context-agnostic audio embeddings trained via representation learning. These embeddings capture acoustic properties and features independent of predefined labels. This was seen to outperform traditional methods like OpenL3 by handling class imbalance and label noise through cross-dataset training and metric learning. While the UCS standardizes libraries, this work complements the system by creating generalized embeddings applicable to both UCS-compliant and non-compliant datasets. Although, this approach does not assign fixed labels like traditional classifiers, instead it retrieves based on acoustic similarity. This approach in a multimodal methodology could be relevant for platforms like Freesound, where user-generated tags often deviate from standards, and provides a proper framework for evaluation.

By adopting the hierarchical taxonomy of UCS as a classification benchmark, our research can address the challenges of classification and taxonomies in Freesound, where inconsistent metadata currently limit search-ability and usability. The deployment of UCS in a real world context, such as the Freesound community-driven tagging system, will help to address many challenges. Chiruthapudi, S. [43] explored sound classification using the Universal Category System (UCS) on the ProSound-Effects dataset, developing and evaluating automatic classifiers based on standard classification metrics to assess their performance. This research extends the previous work by trying to refine and improve the classifiers and evaluating how established UCS classifiers perform under imperfect real-world conditions. By implementing UCS-based classification with Freesound data, we aim to evaluate and research on how community based platforms could potentially benefit from Industry standards, while simultaneously providing further insights and research opportunities into how these taxonomies perform.

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodology used in this thesis to experiment and investigate sound classification using UCS[2] in the context of Freesound. The pipeline consists of comparing different models, development of Freesound dataset, feature extraction from the datasets, evaluation and possible refinements and enhancements of existing classifiers using different architectures, and cross-domain evaluation. The experiments are performed on various levels starting from a small subset of the PSE150K, using which we evaluate various architectures and try to find the most optimal architectures for the experiments. A set of different models were obtained from these evaluations with different multimodal features which were used to finally evaluate cross-domain performance.

3.1 Dataset

3.1.1 PSE150K

The PSE150K dataset is an audio sound effects collection that was developed by Pro Sound Effects (PSE) company. PSE has developed one of the largest library of professionally recorded sounds. For our work we use a dataset that was provided by PSE to the Music Technology Group (MTG) at Pompeu Fabra University[44]. This dataset in total consists of 380,000 audio files which have been categorized according

to the Universal Category System (UCS)[2] of 82 top level categories and 753 sub categories. From this full dataset, we use approximately 143,300 audio files along with which a metadata file of .csv format that contains the mapping of each audio file to its corresponding top-level category, sub-category and category ID which we call as the PSE150k dataset. From dataset analysis, it was noted that across the top level 82 categories, there were 368 unique subcategories. The dataset shows significant variability in category representation, ranging from 43 samples (CERAMICS) to 10,539 samples (VEHICLES). The most populated categories are common sound effects like VEHICLES, AMBIENCE, VOICES, WATER, ANIMALS, while some ambiguous and specialized categories contain fewer samples reflecting the more niche applications in professional usage. Since 143,000 audio files will be computa-

Table 1: Summary of Dataset Statistics for PSE150K and PSE8K

Dataset	Top-level Categories	Sub-categories	Avg. Samples.
PSE150K	82	368	≈ 1747
PSE8K	82	291	≈ 97

tionally expensive to perform evaluations on, we use a smaller subset of this dataset of approximately 8,000 audio files were used to perform a preliminary rapid evaluation of sound classification systems. This subset PSE8K is balanced targeting approximately 100 samples per category across all the 82-top level UCS categories. 74 categories out of the 82 has 100 samples each with some categories varying with lesser numbers like WINDOWS (62 samples), EQUIPMENT(59 samples) etc. This dataset has better class distribution and was used as the base for robust classification model training and evaluations. This dataset serves as the primary dataset representing a professionally curated and controlled dataset.

3.1.2 Freesound Data

Initial Dataset development and limitations

A custom Freesound dataset was created specifically for cross-domain evaluation in this research. The initial phase involved developing a smaller dataset comprising

approximately 1,534 audio clips sourced through the Freesound API. Each audio sample was mapped to the 82 top-level UCS categories and accompanied by comprehensive metadata including Freesound ID, titles, tags, descriptions, and source URLs. The dataset targeted approximately 20 samples per category, using generic search queries that combined top-level category names with relevant synonyms to ensure broad coverage across each class.

However, several limitations emerged during the data collection process. Since the dataset exclusively used only the MP3 files from Freesound rather than files of all formats, the collected data was constrained in both quality and availability. This limitation, combined with the generic nature of search queries, resulted in insufficient samples for some ambiguous top-level categories, ultimately reducing the final dataset to 79 categories out of the original 82. Further analysis revealed significant inconsistencies in audio quality across samples, showing the diversity of recordings and environments used by different Freesound contributors. Additionally, the absence of user-based sampling functionalities led to an unintended bias where multiple samples were collected from the same users, potentially compromising the dataset's diversity and representativeness for robust cross-domain evaluation.

Comprehensive Dataset creation

In order to mitigate these issues with the preliminary dataset, we set out to build a larger dataset that could be used as a base for future work in cross-domain classification from professional datasets to more real-world user-generated content datasets. A comprehensive Freesound dataset was developed for cross-domain evaluation, comprising approximately 9,400 audio files mapped to the 82 top-level UCS categories. The dataset employed a query-based collection methodology utilizing the Freesound API, targeting around 100-120 samples per category. For each UCS category, multiple queries were created using the top-level category as the primary query and subcategories and their synonyms as secondary queries. Each query was structured in the following manner: "<subcategory/synonym> <primary query>". This made the queries very extensive in nature, going through various different possibilities in

each top-level category. The number of samples to be collected from a category was distributed across the queries depending on the number of queries that were present for that respective category. For example, if a category "AIR" had 10 queries, each query would collect 12 samples. These queries were created and mapped across all the categories manually using the UCS[2] categorization available on their website. In order to ensure proper distribution among a category with different queries, fallback strategies were implemented such that if one or more queries did not collect a sufficient amount of samples, the collection was redirected towards the other search queries that were more successful. This process was repeated until each category collected a satisfactory amount of samples.

Additionally, in order to ensure quality and prevent bias in the dataset, some filtering functionalities were implemented. The API allows for only downloads of the previews of the audio files of full length and not the original files in the original format, so preference for high-quality formats was given (WAV > FLAC > MP3), and the preview files were downloaded in .ogg format, which is of higher quality than MP3, the files chosen were filtered to have minimum user ratings of 3 or greater wherever available. In order to prevent bias, global tracking of samples per user across the collection was implemented so that no more than 3 or 4 samples were collected per user across the different categories. This ensured acoustic and metadata diversity in the dataset. Along with the collection of the files, the metadata for each audio file was also collected and stored, which includes the file name, Freesound ID, Freesound URL, UCS category of the respective file, query used, tags, description, uploader information, rating, and audio file information (file format, sample rate). Duplicates were also not allowed to be downloaded. This whole process was automated in a script with oversight and manual supervision of the data collected.

The resulting dataset achieved approximately 120 samples per category, with some ambiguous or specialized categories yielding fewer samples due to limited availability of suitable content on the platform as shown in 3. This comprehensive dataset represents a significant improvement over the preliminary version, establishing a robust and strong foundation for evaluating cross-domain automatic sound classification

Figure 3: Category Distribution in Freesound dataset

performance between professionally curated sound libraries and user-generated audio content from collaborative platforms.

A notable variation emerged between the professional PSE dataset and the user-generated Freesound dataset across data quality and consistency. The audio quality in the Freesound dataset exhibited significant variability across different contributors, reflecting the diverse recording equipment, acoustic environments, and also expertise of individual users. This contrasts with the PSE dataset’s more consistent nature in its samples. The PSE dataset generally contains more consistent types of recordings and quality of audio across the board. A key distinction compared to the other dataset may lie more in the use of manual labeling rather than automatic querying.

Similarly, the metadata quality revealed significant differences between the two datasets. While the PSE dataset maintains comprehensive and standardized metadata with systematic file naming conventions and structured tagging methodologies,

the Freesound dataset’s user-contributed nature showed highly inconsistent meta-data. This inconsistency was reflected throughout the dataset, some users would tag their files with extensive, detailed descriptions while others provided a few words as descriptions. File names ranged from alphanumeric codes to overly verbose descriptions. This stark contrast between the professional, standardized PSE dataset and the chaotic reality of user-generated content perfectly illustrates one of the biggest challenges in audio classification research: training models on professional, curated data only to deploy them in the unpredictable world of user-contributed uploads.

3.1.3 Other datasets

In order to compare UCS with other taxonomies, two other datasets were evaluated - BSD10K (Broad sound Dataset)[4], which contains 10,309 Freesound audio clips, manually annotated according to the Broad Sound Taxonomy which has 5 top-level categories and 23 subcategories. Another dataset that was evaluated is the FSD50K (Freesound Dataset 50K)[39], which contains 51,197 Freesound audio clips that are assigned to different classes aligned with the AudioSet ontology[5]. The AudioSet ontology is a hierarchical taxonomy of 632 sound event classes, developed by Google.

3.2 Feature Extraction

Feature extraction for the datasets were done using LAION CLAP[34]. The CLAP embeddings were used to represent both audio and textual data in a common latent space. The CLAP model provides a 512-dimensional embedding for each audio clip and corresponding text metadata. CLAP embeddings were extracted directly from the waveforms of the audio files using a pre-trained LAION-CLAP encoder for PSE150K and the Freesound data alike. The processing chain begins with audio loading via librosa[45] at a target sampling rate of 48kHz, followed by conversion of the audio into mel spectrograms which is handled by the CLAP model. Each audio file is passed through CLAP’s audio encoder to produce a 512-dimensional feature vector that captures semantic audio representations.

In order to experiment and investigate different modalities, text metadata was pro-

cessed and extracted from the CSV file that had information about each audio file along with its file name, top-level categories and subcategories. For the PSE150K dataset, the metadata was professionally curated and had proper structure, whereas for real-world data like Freesound, the metadata ranged from detailed descriptions and tags to minimal words or incomplete descriptions. The text feature extraction generated descriptions for audio samples. The meaningful keywords from filenames and descriptions were extracted and created into structured descriptions such as "Audio sample with characteristics (keywords) and type (subcategory)" along with some simpler tags, the top level categories and subcategories. These generated text descriptions are passed through CLAP's text encoder to produce 512-dimensional embeddings that share the same space as the audio embeddings. This enabled multimodal comparisons.

The system employs two multimodal fusion strategies to combine audio and text embeddings. Concatenation fusion merges the 512-dimensional audio and text vectors into a 1024-dimensional representation, preserving all information from both modalities. Weighted fusion maintains the original 512-dimensional space by combining modalities with learnable weights, defaulting to 80% audio and 20% text ($\alpha = 0.8$). The same feature extraction pipeline was used on both the PSE150K and Freesound dataset

The subset PSE8K consisted of 7990 audio files in total, and to ensure consistency and completeness, the file names without their extensions were cross-referenced and checked with the files available according to the metadata file from the embeddings extracted from CLAP. This matching procedure revealed that valid embeddings were available for 5,568 audio files within the subset. Since this subset was derived from the bigger full data set of 350K audio files, there ended up being some files that did not have the extracted embeddings. However it was confirmed that more or less the categories were still well balanced and not substantially skewed.

3.3 Classification with dataset subset (PSE8K)

3.3.1 Experimental Design and Model Implementation

To establish baseline performance and explore optimal architectures, initial experiments were conducted on the PSE8K subset, which provided a suitable foundation for rapid evaluation and iterative model development. Several classification models were tested to assess their ability to handle the unique challenges posed by both audio and text data, as well as their combined multimodal embeddings.

The first model evaluated was the **K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)** classifier, implemented, serving as a non-parametric baseline model for classification evaluations, where classification decisions are made by finding the $k = 3$ nearest neighbors of a query point in the embedding space based on cosine distance. Majority voting among these neighbors determines the predicted class. To handle the high-dimensional CLAP embeddings effectively, StandardScaler normalization was applied to standardize the feature space before computation. This model supports multimodal fusion by concatenating audio and text embeddings into a 1024-dimensional vector but also uses audio-only or text-only modes using 512-dimensional inputs. The KNN approach does not involve an explicit training phase but provides valuable insight into the separability of the embedding space and robustness against class imbalance through local majority voting.

The next model implemented was the **Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)**, implemented with feedforward neural network, featuring two hidden layers containing 1024 and 512 neurons, respectively, and applies the tanh activation function for non-linearity. The model training leverages the Adam optimizer with an adaptive learning rate scheduler initialized at $\alpha = 0.001$. L2 regularization with penalty weight $\lambda = 0.001$ reduces overfitting, the model training used early stopping based on validation accuracy for better convergence control. Input features are preprocessed through StandardScaler, while categorical targets utilize Label Encoder encoding. The MLP also similarly supports the audio-only, text-only and the multimodal con-

catenated configurations.

In order to evaluate using advanced machine learning architectures, a **Transformer model** was implemented, designed to use and experiment with the self-attention mechanism for capturing complex sequence relationships in the embeddings. The model projects input features linearly to 256 dimensions, enhanced by learnable positional encodings for sequence structure, followed by a Transformer encoder consisting of 3 layers, each with 8 attention heads and a 256-dimensional model size. The feedforward layers contain 512 units, employing GELU activation and a dropout rate of 0.1 for regularization. The sequence representation is passed through a classification head built from LayerNorm, Dropout, Linear, GELU, and Linear layers. Training utilizes AdamW optimizer with weight decay (0.01), learning rate scheduling based on ReduceLROnPlateau, gradient clipping (max norm 1.0), and early stopping with 10 epochs patience.

Lastly, since we use two multimodal configurations and embeddings, two variants of **cross-attention models** were developed and implemented to explicitly model the interactions between audio and text modalities. The *Standard Cross-Attention* architecture features separate linear input projections for audio and text into a shared 256-dimensional space. It uses bidirectional cross-attention layers to allow audio tokens to attend to text tokens and vice versa, followed by fusion through concatenation and a fusion network, culminating in a linear classification layer. The *Patch-Based Multi-Token Cross-Attention* model further decomposes the 512-dimensional CLAP embeddings into 8 patches of 64 dimensions each, using learnable position embeddings to preserve sequence order within patches. This design enables richer, fine-grained interaction between audio and text through bidirectional patch-level attention and subsequent refinement via Transformer encoder layers. Attention pooling methods synthesize the refined patch features into a compact embedding for classification.

Each model was evaluated across diverse feature configurations: using text-only features derived from CSV metadata, audio-only features from CLAP embeddings, multimodal concatenation forming a 1024-dimensional combined embedding, and

weighted multimodal fusion with the audio feature weight α varying systematically from 0.2 to 0.8.

Architecture Optimization and Validation

To optimize the MLP architecture for the dataset, hyperparameter tuning was conducted using `RandomizedSearchCV` with 10-fold stratified cross-validation. The search space was for hidden layer configurations ranging from single-layer (100-1000 neurons) to two-layer architectures, activation functions (ReLU, tanh, sigmoid), learning rates (0.0001-0.1), regularization strengths (0.0001-0.1), and convergence parameters. Using 50 iterations of random parameter combinations, the tuning process used balanced accuracy as the primary metric to handle class imbalance effectively. `StandardScaler` preprocessing was applied consistently across all configurations, and the final model was selected based on the cross-validation performance.

The systematic exploration confirmed that the (1024, 512) architecture provided optimal performance for the PSE8K dataset, it was complex enough to capture patterns in the data without becoming too complicated and overfitting.

3.4 Large-Scale classification using PSE150K

To train the models and establish performance benchmarks, training and evaluations were conducted on the full PSE150K dataset, which contains approximately 143,000 audio files, using the best-performing MLP architecture identified in prior experiments. The study focused on assessing the classification capabilities of different input modalities, including text-only, audio-only and multimodal models that combine audio and text embeddings, and the weighted fusion models with alpha 0.8. The models were evaluated using a set of metrics: Balanced Accuracy to account for class imbalance, overall standard Accuracy, Macro-F1 and weighted-F1 to account for class distribution. These four model configurations served as the primary baselines for further evaluation on Freesound data, providing a robust framework for understanding the contribution of each modality to sound effect classification performance.

3.5 Evaluation on Freesound Data

In our cross-domain evaluation, the PSE150K dataset[44], professionally curated and controlled served as the training domain, while the comprehensive Freesound UCS dataset with approximately 9400 audio files, with its diverse and user-contributed samples, served as the evaluation domain. To ensure comparability, the evaluation was restricted to categories common to both datasets, which in this case was the top level categories where all the 82 categories matched. A primary challenge addressed was the distribution shift and quality difference between the controlled recordings in PSE and the real-world, user-generated audio in Freesound.

Feature extraction leveraged the LAION-CLAP[34] model, producing 512 dimensional embeddings for both audio and text modalities. Text features combined metadata fields such as title, tags and description. Two multimodal fusion approaches were applied: direct concatenation yielding 1024-dimensional vectors, and weighted fusion combining audio and text embeddings with audio weight of $\alpha = 0.8$.

We evaluated four PSE150K-trained MLP classifiers across different input configurations: audio-only, text-only, multimodal concatenated, and multimodal weighted fusion. The Freesound feature vectors were standardized using scalars trained on PSE150K data, and label encoding was aligned to match category mappings from the training set. Performance was assessed using accuracy, balanced accuracy to account for class imbalance, as well as macro- and weighted-F1 scores.

Results highlighted a consistent performance drop in the cross-domain setting compared to within-domain PSE evaluations, illustrating the domain gap challenge. Different modalities showed varied robustness, with the Audio-only embeddings and multimodal fusion strategies showing better performance against domain-text-only domains.

3.6 Cross-Domain Classification Analysis

To understand how well the models generalize across different audio domains, we conducted a comprehensive analysis focusing on the Freesound UCS dataset as the evaluation domain against models trained on the controlled PSE150K dataset.

3.6.1 Embedding Space Visualization

We used t-SNE visualization to compare embeddings from the PSE and Freesound datasets across four feature configurations: audio-only, text-only, multimodal concatenation, and weighted multimodal fusion. The resulting projections revealed distinct domain clustering patterns, highlighting the presence of significant distribution shifts between professionally curated and user-generated audio data. Notably, text embeddings exhibited different separation characteristics, generally displaying more dispersed class clusters. Audio (CLAP embeddings) and multimodal embeddings demonstrated intermediate behavior, effectively bridging some of the domain gaps observed in unimodal feature spaces.

3.6.2 Cross-Modal Search

To further explore practical applications of the learned embeddings, we implemented interactive search functionalities in two modalities. The search-by-text system extracts text embeddings from real-time queries and predicts categories using trained MLP classifiers. Retrieval is performed by fetching the top-k closest samples within predicted categories, enabling evaluation of cross-modal search effectiveness. Conversely, the search-by-audio system generates audio embeddings directly from query files and conducts similarity searches within the predicted categories, validating the models' ability to perform audio-to-audio retrieval across domain boundaries. Comparative analyses across different model configurations demonstrated the robustness of multimodal embeddings in handling diverse query types.

3.7 Fine-Tuning using Transfer learning

The fine-tuning process was conducted as an additional step to explore the potential for improved domain adaptation and inform possible directions for future work in Automatic Sound Effects Classification. The pre-trained MLP models originally trained on the Pro Sound Effects (PSE) [44] dataset, including audio-only, text-only, multimodal concatenation, and multimodal weighted architectures, were adapted to the Freesound UCS dataset through transfer learning.

For fine-tuning, the pre-trained model weights were transferred and further trained on stratified splits of Freesound UCS data at different percentages of data (10%, 25%, 50%), preserving category balance. The feature extraction process matched that of the original models, using CLAP audio embeddings for audio, combined embeddings from title, description, and tags for text, concatenation for the multimodal concat model, and a weighted sum (with $\alpha=0.8$ for audio) for the multimodal weighted model. To mitigate catastrophic forgetting and leverage existing learned representations, a warm-start was used, with model weights initialized from the pre-trained state, a reduced learning rate (0.1), and continued training for up to 200 iterations.

This fine-tuning step was incorporated to assess the feasibility and effectiveness of transferring domain knowledge from PSE to Freesound, thereby identifying promising paths for future research in this domain.

Chapter 4

Results

This chapter presents the evaluation results obtained from the experiments described in the methodology section. The analysis evaluates model performance across different modalities—audio, text, and multimodal fusion, providing insight into which models achieved the highest and lowest classification accuracy both within the same dataset and in cross-domain scenarios.

4.1 Rapid Evaluation Results

We begin by reporting the results of the rapid evaluation conducted on the PSE8K subset of the full PSE150K dataset. This subset was designed to facilitate efficient experimentation and model iteration by providing a balanced yet manageable collection of audio samples. The PSE8K originally contained 7,990 audio files; however, embeddings could only be successfully extracted for 5,563 of these files due to file availability and processing constraints. Consequently, the evaluation and analysis were restricted to this subset of files with valid embeddings to ensure consistent input representation across all models tested.

While this reduction in sample size potentially impacts the representativeness of the dataset relative to the full PSE150K, the subset retained sufficient category coverage and class balance to provide meaningful preliminary insights into model perfor-

mance. The evaluation used standardized feature extraction pipelines, employing the CLAP[34] model to generate audio and text embeddings, which served as inputs for various classification architectures. This approach enabled rapid benchmarking of different modality-specific and multimodal fusion models under a consistent framework, yielding initial performance results which help guide the subsequent tasks in the project.

4.1.1 Audio-Only Configuration

Table 2: Audio-Only Model Performance on PSE8K

Model Type	Accuracy	Balanced Acc	F1 Macro	F1 Weighted
KNN	0.5202	0.4885	0.4554	0.4913
MLP	0.5701	0.5142	0.4942	0.5499
Transformer	0.5393	0.4829	0.4682	0.5245
Standard CA	0.5509	0.5042	0.4845	0.5365
Patch CA	0.5298	0.4818	0.4631	0.5134

Best Audio-Only: MLP (Accuracy = 0.5701)

4.1.2 Text-Only Configuration

Table 3: Text-Only Model Performance on PSE8K

Model Type	Accuracy	Balanced Acc	F1 Macro	F1 Weighted
KNN	0.8431	0.8432	0.8427	0.8410
MLP	0.9097	0.9106	0.9106	0.9092
Transformer	0.9069	0.9079	0.9078	0.9074
Standard CA	0.9042	0.9045	0.9034	0.9036
Patch CA	0.8972	0.8984	0.8976	0.8966

Best Text-Only: MLP (Accuracy = 0.9097)

4.1.3 Multimodal Concatenation

Table 4: Multimodal Concatenation Model Performance on PSE8K

Model Type	Accuracy	Balanced Acc	F1 Macro	F1 Weighted
KNN	0.7965	0.7572	0.7466	0.7854
MLP	0.9002	0.8773	0.8733	0.8941
Transformer	0.9079	0.8844	0.8760	0.9057
Standard CA	0.9021	0.8797	0.8784	0.8963
Patch CA	0.8983	0.8663	0.8647	0.8944

Best Multimodal Concatenation: Transformer (Accuracy = 0.9079)

4.1.4 Multimodal Weighted Fusion (alpha=0.8)

Table 5: Multimodal Weighted Fusion Model Performance on PSE8K

Model Type	Accuracy	Balanced Acc	F1 Macro	F1 Weighted
KNN	0.5739	0.5425	0.5090	0.5486
MLP	0.6833	0.6379	0.6346	0.6699
Transformer	0.6583	0.6064	0.5807	0.6409
Standard CA	0.8848	0.8617	0.8600	0.8776
Patch CA	0.8983	0.8775	0.8760	0.8925

Best Multimodal Weighted Fusion: Patch Cross-Attention (Accuracy = 0.8983)

4.1.5 Model Performance Analysis

Audio-Only Embeddings Among the audio-only models, the MLP) achieved the highest accuracy at 57.01%, with a balanced accuracy of 51.42%, outperforming other architectures including K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Transformer variants. The MLP also recorded the leading F1 scores, with a Macro F1 of 49.42% and a Weighted F1 of 54.99%, indicating its better capability in capturing prominent audio

features from the CLAP embeddings. While the KNN model showed the lowest performance with an accuracy of 52.02%.

Text-Only Embeddings Text-based models demonstrated significantly higher performance than audio-only counterparts. The MLP model again achieved the highest with an accuracy of 90.97%, balanced accuracy of 91.06%, and high Macro and Weighted F1 scores nearing 91%, showcasing the model’s ability to learn from metadata and the textual description features. Transformer and Cross-Attention models also performed similarly well with negligible difference compared to the MLP, achieving accuracies in the 90% range. The KNN model, while lowest among these, still reached an accuracy of 84.31%.

Figure 4: Balanced Accuracy across different models

Multimodal Concatenation Combining audio and text embeddings via simple concatenation improved overall performance across all models. The Transformer model topped this group with a 90.79% accuracy and balanced accuracy of 88.44%, followed closely by MLP and Cross-Attention models. The KNN model also showed gains over audio-only mode, reaching nearly 80% accuracy, possibly indicating some advantage in using multimodal embeddings.

Multimodal Weighted Fusion (alpha=0.8) When applying weighted fusion with a dominant audio weight of 0.8, the Cross-Attention models performed best by

a notable margin. Patch Cross-Attention attained an accuracy of 89.83%, balanced accuracy of 87.75%, and F1 scores above 87%. The Standard Cross-Attention model similarly recorded high scores around 88% accuracy. Other models including MLP and Transformer saw decreased accuracies with 68% and 65% respectively compared to concatenation. KNN demonstrated its lowest performance here, around 57% accuracy.

Overall, these results demonstrate that the MLP consistently achieved the best performance despite its relatively simpler architecture compared to more complex models such as Transformers and Cross-Attention networks. This trend held true across most feature configurations, with the exception of the weighted multimodal fusion setting, where the cross-attention models exhibited stronger performance. Further details and analysis of this exception are provided in the Discussion section.

4.2 Evaluation of full dataset

The full PSE150K dataset was evaluated using the best-performing MLP model identified from the subset experiments across different embedding configurations. The training and evaluation in this section are conducted exclusively with MLP architectures, leveraging their demonstrated effectiveness. This approach allows us to use on the strengths of the MLP model while scaling evaluation to the entire dataset, providing a comprehensive assessment of model performance on a broader dataset. The trained MLP models will be further utilized for cross-domain evaluation tasks, including experiments on the Freesound dataset.

Table 6: PSE150K Model Performance (MLP Architectures)

Model	Accuracy	Bal Acc	F1 Macro	F1 Weighted
Text-Only	0.9833	0.9796	0.9805	0.9833
Multimodal Concat	0.9838	0.9808	0.9810	0.9837
Multimodal Weighted	0.8344	0.8070	0.8037	0.8335
Audio-Only	0.6746	0.6270	0.6409	0.6720

The performance of the MLP model evaluated across four embedding configurations

on the full PSE150K dataset is presented in 6 and visualized in the confusion matrices shown in Figure 5. The multimodal concatenation configuration yielded the highest accuracy at 98.38%, with corresponding balanced accuracy and F1 scores exceeding 98%. The text-only configuration showed high accuracy as well, with an accuracy of 98.33% and balanced accuracy of 97.96%. In both these settings, the confusion matrices (Figure 5b and 5c) display strong diagonal dominance, indicating near perfect classification across nearly all categories; however, this displayed performance may overestimate the model’s true effectiveness given the complexity of the classification task and might not fully reflect the challenges of the task, and the results should be interpreted with caution.

In contrast, the multimodal weighted fusion configuration, employing an audio weight of 0.8, resulted in reduced performance, with accuracy and balanced accuracy values around 83%. The corresponding confusion matrix (Figure 5d) reveals an increase in off-diagonal errors, suggesting higher misclassification rates compared to concatenated or text-only embeddings.

The audio-only configuration produced the lowest metrics, recording an accuracy of 67.46% and a balanced accuracy of 62.70%. Its confusion matrix (Figure 5) further illustrates a significant presence of off-diagonal elements, highlighting increased confusion between categories when relying solely on audio features, which more accurately reflects the challenges typical of audio classification tasks.

Collectively, these results provide valuable insight into the behavior of the different embedding modalities. The audio-based CLAP embeddings appear to offer a more realistic representation of the classification challenges inherent in audio data, while the text embeddings tend to produce more optimistic performance estimates that may overstate model capabilities. Building on these observations, the trained models were applied to cross-domain evaluation on the Freesound dataset to further assess their generalization capabilities beyond the original training distribution.

Figure 5: Confusion matrices for MLP evaluation of (a) Audio-only, (b) Text-only, (c) Multimodal concatenated, and (d) Multimodal weighted configurations.

4.3 Evaluation of PSE trained models on Freesound Data

The PSE-trained models were evaluated on two versions of the Freesound dataset: a preliminary subset and an extended, more comprehensive collection. This evaluation involved a number of different experiments designed to compare model performance and provide detailed analysis across different embedding configurations. The aim was to assess the generalization capability of the trained models when applied to external, real-world audio datasets with varying characteristics.

4.3.1 Results on Preliminary Freesound Dataset

The evaluation results on the preliminary Freesound-UCS dataset are described below. The overall model performance across all embedding modalities and fusion strategies is significantly lower compared to the PSE150K evaluations, reflecting the increased complexity and variability of the Freesound data.

Among the different configurations, the **multimodal concat. model** achieved the **highest accuracy of 16.71%**, alongside balanced accuracy and F1 metrics exceeding 15%. The audio-only model also performed competitively, with an accuracy of 16.02%, marginally below the multimodal concatenation. The multimodal weighted fusion and text-only models yielded slightly lower accuracies, around 15.5% and 12.0% as the lowest for the text-only model respectively. This preliminary evaluation provides a valuable baseline for further development of an extended freesound dataset with a more diverse sample set, allowing for more comprehensive and reliable evaluation of model performance.

4.3.2 Results on Extended Freesound Dataset

The extended Freesound UCS dataset used for evaluation comprises approximately 9,400 audio files across the 82 top-level UCS[2] sound categories, with an average of about 120 samples per category. This dataset offers a diverse and representative

collection of real-world audio samples, making it a challenging benchmark for large-scale, multi-class sound classification.

The evaluation results as shown in 7 reveal that model performance on this dataset, while modest, reflects the inherent complexity and variability within Freesound samples. Among the four embedding configurations tested, the **multimodal weighted fusion** approach achieved the highest accuracy of approximately **28.7%**, **balanced accuracy** around 28%, and F1 weighted score close to 26.8%. Multimodal concatenation followed with comparable but slightly lower performance, with accuracy around 26.1%. The audio-only model showed moderate effectiveness with an accuracy near 23.8%, and the text-only model recorded the lowest metrics, with accuracy slightly above 20.1%.

Table 7: Freesound-UCS Evaluation Results Summary

Model	Accuracy	Bal Acc	F1 Macro	F1 Weighted
Audio-Only	0.2383	0.2323	0.2209	0.2262
Text-Only	0.2057	0.1974	0.1902	0.1971
Multimodal Concat	0.2602	0.2507	0.2412	0.2484
Multimodal Weighted	0.2872	0.2801	0.2688	0.2751

These results seem to indicate a trend where combining audio and textual features seems to enhance classification capability despite the dataset’s complexity. As shown by the confusion matrices in Figure 6, all model configurations exhibit substantial off-diagonal errors, highlighting frequent misclassifications across many of the 82 top-level categories. While the multimodal approaches outperform single-modality models, the absolute scores remain modest, indicating persistent challenges in achieving robust generalization.

The relatively lower scores across all models point out the major challenge of generalization when moving from controlled and professional datasets to a diverse and varied heterogeneous collection like Freesound UCS Dataset. The rich diversity of sounds, annotation variability, and domain mismatch between training and testing data likely contribute to these outcomes.

Overall, these findings provide a comprehensive perspective on model performance

Figure 6: Confusion matrices for evaluation on Freesound dataset (a) Audio-only, (b) Text-only, (c) Multimodal concatenated, and (d) Multimodal weighted configurations.

and generalization under realistic automatic Sound classification conditions. The results and visual analysis suggest key directions for future research, particularly in refining embeddings, improving fusion strategies, and addressing domain adaptation challenges for large-scale, multi-class sound recognition. Taken together, the results provide a foundation for a lot of interpretation of the model behavior in sound classification and the broader implications of cross-domain sound classifications. These aspects will be explored further in greater detail in the following Discussion section.

4.4 Fine-tuning Results

Fine-tuning consistently improved model performance across all configurations and training data percentages, the accuracies of different training data used for the fine-tuning is shown in figure 7. With just 10% of Freesound UCS data, each model slightly outperformed its original PSE baseline, and more improvements were observed as more training data was used. The audio-only model accuracy increased moderately, from 24.3% at 10% data to 25.0% at 50%. For the text-only model, gains were a bit more pronounced, jumping from 21.2% to 23.7%. Multimodal models achieved the best results overall: the concatenation model rose from 26.8% to 29.0%, and the weighted multimodal model achieved the highest accuracy, from 29.6% to 30.2% as training data increased from 10% to 50%.

These findings demonstrate that fine-tuning is especially effective for multimodal systems and that performance benefits scale with the size of the target dataset.

Figure 7: Fine-Tuned model accuracies

Chapter 5

Discussion

The discussion section serves as the critical part of the thesis where the implications and significance of the research findings is interpreted and explored within the broader scientific context. It begins by restating the research objectives and summarizing the key results, providing a foundation for further analysis. This section then explores the implications of the findings, discusses how they align with or challenge existing literature, acknowledges limitations, and outlines potential directions for future research.

5.1 Rapid Evaluation on Dataset Subset

The rapid evaluations on the PSE8K dataset was performed in order to find and possibly enhance previous research findings [43]. These evaluations were performed on embeddings extracted using CLAP for the Pro sound Effects (PSE) dataset [44]. Additionally text embeddings were extracted from the metadata available along with the PSE dataset.

First, the MLP consistently outperforms or performs with negligible difference compared to more complex architectures such as Transformers and Cross-Attention models in most configurations. A simpler architecture like MLP with just 2 layers performing on par with complex models such as transformers and Cross-attention

models when trained on CLAP[34] embeddings is possibly due to the CLAP embeddings being highly informative feature representations. CLAP embeddings are generated using complex neural network encoders trained with contrastive language-audio training on massive datasets. This training results in the embeddings inherently being complex and descriptive in a structured form. Because of this a straightforward model like MLP can leverage these embeddings without requiring the complexity of models like transformers or Cross-attention networks. Such complex architectures possibly risk overfitting due to their larger parameter spaces and may struggle with already well-processed inputs. Such complex models might benefit from using the raw audio or even a bigger dataset as inputs without being redundant.

A critical issue relates to the overly optimistic performance of the text-only and multimodal embedding configurations. The dataset used contains well-curated and uniform textual metadata with keyword-rich embeddings and category and subcategory information. This textual information which were used as the embeddings possibly is due to data leakage and gives a shortcut for the prediction of the classes, which in turn inflates the classification accuracy for models using the text embeddings or multimodal fusion. In contrast, audio-only models based on CLAP embeddings give a more realistic and representation of the model's performance, since audio features are less directly tied to category labels, they genuinely learn and generalize from the underlying semantic audio patterns in the embeddings.

One notable exception from the results is the multimodal weighted fusion setting, where Cross-Attention models performed better by a margin compared to the other models. The weighted fusion embeddings were structured to emphasize audio, but cross-attention mechanisms not being restricted to static balance, can learn to focus on the more predictive features. Given the overly optimistic predictions from the text embeddings, it is possible that the models likely give greater attention towards the text embeddings, thus ending up with better performance. This in properly curated multimodal settings could be an advantage as cross-attention models could leverage one embedding's predictions when the other fails in a certain way.

In conclusion, the results show that MLPs work well as simple and effective classifiers

on CLAP audio embeddings, while cross-attention models are particularly useful when combining modalities in a weighted fusion setting. At the same time, the findings highlight the need to carefully consider how informative text embeddings are, since they can strongly influence classification performance and may give an overly optimistic view of a model’s true capabilities.

5.2 Training and Evaluation on the full dataset

The best MLP architecture previously defined from the rapid evaluations was used as the primary architecture for training and evaluating the PSE150K [44] dataset. Four different models were trained on the full dataset with using different embedding configurations same as above - audio-only, text-only, multimodal concatenated and multimodal weighted fusion.

The results on the full PSE150K dataset reinforce the contrast between modalities seen in the earlier subset experiments. MLP models reached almost perfect performance for both text-only and multimodal concatenation, with accuracies above 98%. While impressive, these results need to be treated with caution. The dataset’s metadata being very well structured, the embeddings extracted from the textual data make it easy for models to “shortcut” directly to the labels. This creates overly optimistic predictions, as classification is strongly biased by the text embeddings.

In comparison, models trained only on audio-based CLAP embeddings achieved lower accuracy compared to the near perfect accuracies from text and multimodal fusions, with around 67%. However, this reflects the real difficulty of sound classification, where models must learn to distinguish complex acoustic patterns along with semantic meaning in the case of CLAP. The confusion matrices for the audio-only models further highlight this challenge, showing greater overlap across categories.

The multimodal weighted fusion approach, which gives more weight to audio, achieved intermediate results. This suggests that emphasizing the audio signal reduces the label shortcut effect of text, but performance remains limited by the inherent complexity of audio classification.

Taken together, these findings highlight the importance of being critical when interpreting high scores from text or multimodal models on structured datasets. They also show why audio-only evaluations are essential for a more realistic view of model robustness and generalization. Additionally, this also shows that audio classification systems cannot be performed based solely on true audio-only or text-only embeddings. A complimentary relationship between semantic and acoustic features is essential in order to actually learn and understand an audio sample. Finally, the consistent success of MLPs across all embedding types reinforces their value as a simple, efficient, and effective choice for large-scale audio classification.

5.3 Evaluation on Freesound Data

5.3.1 Preliminary Dataset Evaluation

The preliminary smaller dataset evaluation results initially showed a substantial drop in performance compared to evaluation on the PSE dataset [44]. In this evaluation, the models with the audio-only configurations and the multimodal fusion ones performed similar to each other with approximately 16% accuracies. On the other hand the text-only model performed worse with only 11% accuracy compared to the other models. Even though overall cross-domain performance seems poor, the text-only being worse shows the significant domain gap between how textual information is in the PSE dataset and the Freesound dataset. Acoustic features on the other hand can usually generalize better and move towards similar embedding space.

Unlike the PSE dataset, Freesound’s textual metadata being user generated is inconsistent and even incomplete at times. The tags are non-standardized, sometimes extensive in nature and sometimes sparse, which explains why text-only models perform worse. The fact that audio-only and multimodal models performed similarly suggests that acoustic features provide a more stable representation across domains than text.

Upon further analysis of the dataset, it was noticed that the audio samples in this

preliminary dataset did not entirely represent every UCS category properly, having only an average of 20 samples per dataset, we could not be sure that the evaluation was comprehensive in nature and showed actual true results as some categories had sounds that did not exactly match that particular class. This indicated the need for a more comprehensive extended dataset for the cross-domain evaluation that could truly represent Freesound data as a test set.

5.4 Comprehensive Dataset Evaluation

After the preliminary evaluation of the PSE[44] trained models on the smaller Freesound dataset, a more comprehensive and balanced dataset was created according to the UCS [2] categories. Across the 82 UCS categories there was a total of approximately 9400 audio files, averaging around 110 samples per category. This dataset proved to be a more accurate representation of the Freesound content with a wide variety of sounds as well as metadata collected along with it such as the file name, textual descriptions, tags, uploader and the rest of the track-specific metadata collected. All four models of different embedding strategies was used to evaluate on this dataset directly without any domain adaptation.

The extended evaluation on the Freesound UCS dataset offers critical insights into the realities and challenges of automatic sound classification in complex, open-domain environments. The results reveal that, even different advanced embedding strategies and multimodal fusion methodologies, the absolute performance remains modest, with the best model being the multimodal weighted model achieving about 28.7% accuracy across 82 diverse sound categories. However this was a notable improvement in the results compared to initial evaluations with the smaller Freesound dataset as the highest accuracy achieved with that was only around 16.7% with the multimodal concatenated. However with the extended dataset we notice that the multimodal audio weighted concatenation ($\alpha = 0.8$) performs the best and the multimodal concatenated embeddings comes a close second with 26%. This points out a key point in the research, the multimodal fusion embeddings seem to give better performance than the more direct text embeddings and the semantic audio

embeddings from CLAP [34].

CLAP embeddings themselves are inherently multimodal in nature as CLAP is trained to capture both acoustic and semantic information. However the CLAP [34] embeddings gave only an accuracy of 23% which is lesser than the multimodal fusion models. This performance boost likely stems from the additional cues provided by the training on the text metadata, which can supplement audio-derived representations in the cases where textual or acoustic features alone are insufficient.

However, overall the results are still nowhere near ideal for the task of Automatic Sound Classification and underscores the challenges in generalization of sounds when the data is unstructured, varying in quality and noisy in nature. The confusion matrices (see figure 6 highlight how there is still substantial misclassifications, showing how there's high category overlap and the nuances of real-world sounds.

5.4.1 t-SNE Analysis of Embedding Spaces Across Domains

Figure 8 presents a t-SNE visualization comparing PSE (blue) and Freesound (red) embeddings across audio-only, text-only, multimodal concatenation, and weighted multimodal configurations. This analysis offers an intuitive window into the distributional properties and domain overlap of each embedding type.

Audio-only (Top Left) t-SNE plot shows pretty high overlap and closer clusters between the PSE [44] and Freesound [1] embeddings, with some clear regions existing where dataset-specific clusters remain. This suggests CLAP audio embeddings capture some similar features, and acoustic variability between curated (PSE) and user-generated (Freesound) data produces not much separation. The somewhat intermixed pattern indicates that audio embeddings provide limited domain generalization, echoing observed model performance. However, the overlap does not necessarily indicate that the embeddings align meaningfully with the intended semantic categories. Rather it may simply reflect low-level acoustic similarities while differences in other factors may remain underrepresented

Figure 8: t-SNE analysis of PSE vs Freesound Embeddings

Text-only (Top Right). For text-only embeddings, the separation between the two datasets is much more pronounced. PSE samples cluster tightly towards the center, reflecting clean and uniform metadata, while Freesound points are more distributed, indicative of noise, heterogeneity, and inconsistent metadata. This explains the significant domain gap and the lower performance with the text-only model.

Multimodal Concatenation (Bottom Left). The multimodal concatenated space exhibits more overlap than text-only, yet some distinction between domains persists. Here, the combined cues from audio and text bring the two domains closer, but simple fusion does not completely align the respective embedding distributions.

Weighted Multimodal Fusion (Bottom Right). The t-SNE plot for weighted multimodal embeddings (with audio weight $\alpha = 0.8$) resembles the audio-only configuration, showing increased mixing of the two datasets. While more domain overlap is achieved, clear separation remains, signifying that even strong audio fusion cannot fully bridge domain gaps present in real-world data.

Overall, the t-SNE analysis visualizes the challenges of domain adaptation: only partial embedding overlap is achieved across configurations, with audio or multimodal

representations providing the greatest (but still incomplete) generalization. It is to be noted that the analysis of Freesound vs PSE was done using only 10,000 PSE samples out of the full dataset and the full Freesound dataset, in order to maintain comparability.

5.4.2 Category Analysis: Performance Across Sound Classes

To further understand model strengths and weaknesses, a detailed category-wise analysis was conducted, as depicted in Figures 9 and 10.

Figure 9 presents the accuracy scores of audio-only, text-only, and multimodal models across all categories. The plot reveals variation in performance between categories and modalities. Some categories such as *Fireworks*, *User Interface*, and *Water* exhibit strong performance, often showing clear benefits from multimodal integration (green bars). In contrast, several categories (e.g., *Natural Disaster*, *Destruction*, *Archived*) show consistently low accuracy across all configurations, suggesting that both modalities struggle to capture discriminative features for these more ambiguous classes. It is to be noted that the "archived" category in the UCS system is a special top-level label meant for sound files that are stored or set aside, not classified by semantic or audio characteristics, making it not so relevant for our current study. The audio-only and multimodal fusion modalities overall show higher per-category performance across the board while the text-only embeddings show good performance only in certain categories like *Cartoon* and *Cloth*.

Figure 10 highlights this further by relating multimodal accuracy to the number of samples per category and annotating categories based on which modality dominated performance. Categories marked in blue (audio dominant) demonstrate that acoustic features are the main contribution to correct predictions, while red (text dominant) points indicate categories where metadata and textual cues give models an edge. Green points (multimodal benefit) illustrate classes where fusing modalities yields the best results. Many categories, especially those with larger sample sizes, benefit from multimodal approaches, yet a sizable number of classes remain challenging, regardless of modality or dataset size.

Figure 9: Category-wise accuracy for audio-only, text-only, and multimodal models.

Figure 10: Multimodal accuracy vs. sample count by category.

Taken together, these analyses reveal several key trends: (1) classification success is highly category-dependent, (2) the better performance from multimodal fusion are not uniform and depend on the complementary nature of audio and textual information per class, and (3) for especially difficult or ambiguous categories, neither modality nor increased data alone solves the challenge, pointing to the need for richer representations or targeted data augmentation. This analysis illustrates the potential and limitations of current multimodal systems, possibly guiding future work towards more robust strategies.

5.5 Fine-Tuning Analysis

Figure 11: Comparison of Fine-tuned Models Based on Accuracy.

Fine-tuning was done on the PSE trained models with 3 different sets of dataset taken from the comprehensive Freesound dataset - 10%, 25%, 50%. Here the plots 11 12 impact of fine-tuning the models. As shown in Figure 11 even modest increments in the amount of data yield measurable improvements over the baseline performance for all the model configurations. Multimodal concatenation and text-only models benefit the most, with gains exceeding 2-3% at the largest fine-tuning split, while audio-only and multimodal weighted models see more modest but consistent improvement.

Figure 12: Fine-tuning Accuracy Improvement Trends.

The line plot of accuracy gains points out the importance of using slightly larger fine-tuning sets. All modalities display steadily increasing improvements, with the largest effect seen for configurations that use "more" textual data. This reinforces how much the difference in textual metadata is present between the two datasets PSE[44] and Freesound[1].

This points out the significance of ideally employing both professionally curated datasets and more varied, real-world datasets for domain adaptation, which will enable models to better generalize between them and remain robust in practical applications where data, that is sounds in this case come in all shapes and sizes.

5.6 Future Work

This study highlights key directions for advancing automatic sound classification:

- Improved Embeddings:** Current audio and text embeddings capture limited real-world variability. Future work should focus on developing more robust, semantically rich representations to enhance generalization. Possibly experimenting using other feature extractors other than CLAP.[34]

- **Advanced Fusion Techniques:** While multimodal fusion improves accuracy, more dynamic and adaptive fusion methods are needed to better leverage modality-specific strengths on a per-sample basis.
- **Diverse and Realistic Data:** Evaluation on heterogeneous datasets like Freesound UCS is a vital and crucial step in creating robust Automatic Sound Classification Systems while also being able to understand well-structured data as well. Expanding dataset diversity and quality will help models better reflect real-world complexities.
- **Domain Adaptation and Robustness:** Addressing domain mismatch, annotation noise, and acoustic diversity remains a challenge. Incorporating domain adaptation, label alignment, and contextual supervision will be important for scalable sound classification systems.
- **Category-aware Modeling:** Although a complex and difficult task, developing category-specific strategies and targeted data augmentation may further enhance performance on challenging or underrepresented sound classes.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

This thesis set out to investigate the challenges of automatic sound classification when moving from controlled, professionally curated datasets to the messier realities of real-world data. On the curated professional dataset, audio embeddings and audio-text models performed strongly, showing the promise of current architectures. Yet when applied to the more varied and unpredictable Freesound dataset, performance dropped noticeably, pointing out the obvious issue of domain-gaps. Semantic audio embeddings showed modest but realistic performance, while multimodal fusion (audio+text) configurations performed relatively better. By contrast, text-only embeddings, though overly optimistic on the professional dataset, failed substantially on Freesound data. To explore this further, fine-tuning on different amounts of Freesound data showed clear improvements, especially for multimodal models, highlighting how critical adaptation is when facing real-world variability. Together, these findings suggest that curated datasets provide a strong foundation, but true robustness comes from handling noisy, diverse data to better prepare models for the complexity of everyday audio.

Ultimately, this thesis contributes to the ongoing challenges in sound classification and emphasizes the need for robust embeddings and domain-aware training strategies as essential steps toward building scalable, transferable, and reliable Automatic Sound FX Classification Systems for real-world use

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